

**Publish OA:
Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable 5)
30 January 2024**

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Overview

Audience:

- **Internal communication:** working groups (WGs), project affiliates, National Open Research Forum (NORF), Royal Irish Academy (RIA)
- **External communication:** publishers, readers, authors, funders, wider OA community

Scope

This plan covers social media, online presence, traditional media (print/radio), and reporting to ensure dissemination of the project's mission and outputs.

Track impact

1. WG members use the impact checklist (saved on [Workspace](#) in the Moodle site) to assess if the event/topic they are involved with should be tracked for the project and if so, how.
2. Any photos, etc., being used by WG members to track project impact should be saved in the relevant WG impact folders on Moodle.
3. The project manager will keep a list throughout the year of events/meetings WG members attended/participated in.
4. WG members should alert the research assistant ASAP on interesting items to Tweet about.

Timeline: 1 November 2022 to 1 November 2024

Communication channels

1. VISUAL IDENTITY

- a. Logo pack created by RIA designer.
- b. PowerPoint presentation template created by RIA designer.
- c. Report template for Publish OA documents created by project manager.

2. PUBLISH OA WEBSITE

Channel: www.publishoa.ie

Audiences: partner organisations, target groups
(publishers/authors/readers/librarians), media

Modus operandi:

- a. Website created from public-facing page on [Moodle](#)
- b. Sections and drop-down menus added for:
 - i. **About:** Project, People, Partners & affiliates, Funding and Contact
 - ii. **Resources:** Links, Outputs (project deliverables), Glossary
 - iii. **News:** External events presented at (e.g. Publishing Ireland), Publish OA Webinars (e.g. on national publishing platforms), future Publish OA events/webinars/workshops
- c. Use Google Analytics to track website traffic and report for impact.

3. SOCIAL MEDIA

Channel: [@PublishOAire](https://twitter.com/PublishOAire) X/Twitter account created (31 May 2023)

Audiences: partner organisations, target groups
(publishers/authors/readers/librarians/researchers), media

Modus operandi:

- a. Banner image created by RIA designer
- b. Project bio/tags added
- c. First Tweet agreed by WG5
- d. Relevant accounts followed (RIA, Trinity Long Room Hub (TLRH), OA organisations, other NORF projects, WG members, affiliate partners, suggestions from WGs) and tagged to build network and communicate with
- e. Post about forthcoming Publish OA events or deliverables
- f. Tweet about significant OA/publishing/public funding, etc., issues
- g. Retweet relevant posts
- h. Use relevant hashtags (e.g. #OpenAccess, #LoveIrishResearch), and tag in relevant accounts (e.g. project members/stakeholders, NORF, DRI, Dept of Higher Education, Open Access Publishers, Irish academic publishers, Publishing Ireland, Books Ireland, DIAMAS, PALOMERA, etc.)
- i. As at 30 January 2024: [245 following](#), [193 followers](#)

4. NEWSLETTERS AND BLOGS

Channels: Moodle newsletter via [Announcements](#) (internal), partner newsletters (e.g. [TCD](#), [NORF](#), [Publishing Ireland](#) & [RIA](#)), partner blogs (e.g. [NORF](#))

Audiences: funders, partner organisations, target groups (publishers/authors/readers/librarians), media

Frequency:

- **Newsletters:** internal (Moodle), external, can propose items for inclusion on a monthly basis
- **Blogs:** as a suitable topic arises – an event or a deliverable

5. NEWSPAPERS/NEWS SITES

Channels: Newspapers and news sites (e.g. [Irish Times](#), [Books Ireland](#), RTE Opinion piece).

Audiences: funders, partner organisations, target groups (publishers/authors/readers/librarians/researchers), media.

Modus operandi: pitch appropriate venue for significant events/outputs that would raise the profile of the project on a case-by-case basis.

6. CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS:

Channels: Publish OA [webinars/events](#) or attendance/participation in external events.

Audiences: funders, partner organisations, target groups (publishers/authors/readers/librarians), media.

Modus operandi:

- a. Events attended or presented at are logged in the [Tracking impact](#) spreadsheet on SharePoint
- b. Potential forthcoming items are also added to this sheet and are discussed periodically by WG5 so events can be targeted
- c. Once events are agreed, expenditure is estimated and sent to WG1 for approval

Events in 2023:

See the [mid-term report](#) for a list of events participated in/attended in 2023.

Events for 2024:

- See the list published on the [Publish OA website](#).
- Possible recurring events (see below)
- Future suggestions by WG members

Recurring annual events:

- [Open Collaboration for Community-Driven Scholarly Communication \(OPERAS\)](#), Zadar, April (deadline passed)
- [Library Publishing Forum](#), Minneapolis, May (deadline for proposals: 15 December)
- [OAI, Geneva](#), September (no submission details as yet)
- Pubmet, September (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))
- OpenAIRE Open Science Fair, September (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))
- [Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers \(ALPSP\)](#), Manchester, September
- [Frankfurt Book Fair](#), October
- International Open Access Week, October (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))

Post-project events:

- NORFest, November (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))
- Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing, online and in Tromsø, November (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))
- Publishing Ireland Trade Day, November (no details as yet - 2023 conference [info](#))

7. GOVERNANCE REPORTING

Channels: Reports to NORF and the RIA Publications Committee

Audiences: funder, leading organisation

Modus operandi:

- a. Annually (mid-term and full-term reports) to NORF with monthly verbal reports by all projects.
- b. Quarterly reports by WG1 to the RIA Publications Committee, which reports annually to the Council of the Academy.
- c. WG1 liaison with NORF as required, as per its terms of reference (see [WP1 section](#) on Moodle).

8. PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

- a. Potential articles identified by WG members.
- b. If opinion pieces, they may be written without explicitly mentioning the project if topics covered may be sensitive to stakeholders.
- c. Any articles will not be reviewed by the WGs, but the project manager should be informed so any potential issues can be identified, or authors directed to any relevant information.

9. DELIVERABLES

Published with a DOI on the project website under [Outputs](#), as per the schedule outlined in the project Gantt chart housed under the [WG1 folder](#) on SharePoint.
